

ABSTRACT BOOK

14TH CONGRESS OF THE EUROPEAN PAIN FEDERATION EFIC®

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PAIN IN EUROPE XIV

COMORBIDITY OF CHRONIC PAIN AND MENTAL
HEALTH DISORDERS: BREAKING THE CYCLE

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Results = 94.4% of patients more than 30% pain reduction and 82.4% of patients more than 50% pain reduction.

This ensures control of back pain.

Excellent safety in patients with chronic back pain.

Study type: 5 Randomized trials; Duloxetine 60 -120 mg/day.

No. Of patients: 625 patients with chronic low back pain.

Duration: 4 weeks.

Results = 0% incidence of gastrointestinal, renal or cardiovascular side effects.

0% incidence of drug abuse/ addiction.

Conclusions: This is safe and devoid of Side effects of NSAIDs and opioids and has anti depressant efficacy. The development of Duloxetine allows further optimisation of individual treatment strategies so as to provide more therapeutic choices.

I-C.21

OBJECTIVE MEASUREMENT OF PHYSICAL ACTIVITY PATTERNS IN CHRONIC PAIN

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Background and aims: While physical activity (PA) is an important factor in chronic pain, caregivers have difficulty in assessing PA-behavior. Moreover, associations between subjective (e.g. questionnaires) and objective measures (e.g. accelerometers) are inconsistent and no obvious differences exist in total PA in CP versus healthy controls. This emphasizes the need for detailed assessment of PA-patterns. This study aims to develop and validate a machine learning model (MLM) to convert accelerometer data to activity intensity timeseries and compare performance with a traditional method.

Methods: The MLM was trained and tested with labelled activity bouts from 30 healthy participants (HP) and 30 CPP. Each participant performed 22 classified activities (sedentary, low, moderate or vigorous) in epochs of 80 seconds with a wrist-worn tri-axial accelerometer. Performance was evaluated and compared with a conventional cut-off points approach. The resulting MLM was applied to real-life accelerometer timeseries. The output was compared with 1707 one-minute observations as a gold-standard.

Results: Accuracy and precision of the MLM for classifying activity intensity were both 0.82, while these values for the traditional cut-off point approach were 0.54 and 0.35. MLM-agreement in the four intensity classes ranged from 0.68 to 0.91. In real-life conditions accuracy was 0.72 and agreement ranged from 0.62 to 0.82 in the four classes. Barcoding was used for visualization of activity intensity timeseries.

Conclusions: The MLM accurately and precisely classified data from a wrist-worn tri-axial accelerometer in four classes of activity intensity in HP and CPP. Criterion validity was good. The MLM clearly outperformed the cut-off points approach.

I-C.22

ARE THERE ANY DIFFERENCES IN PAIN THRESHOLDS DURING MENSTRUAL CYCLE?

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Background and aims: Pain is a sensory and emotional experience, making its perception highly variable among individuals. In women, pain perception can vary with hormonal changes during different phases of the menstrual cycle (MC). Additionally, significant fluctuations in emotional status can occur during these phases. The aim of this study was to determine the difference in pressure pain thresholds (PPT) in women during different phases of the MC. The additional goal was to assess differences in emotional status.

Methods: Follicular phase (FP) and luteal phase (LP) of the MC were determined using an online ovulation calculator. The study included 95 participants (average age 27.7±7.8 years). Since only 5 of the subjects were in ovulation, we did not include them in further analysis. PPT testing was conducted on the m. extensor carpi radialis longus and the paraspinal musculature of the lumbar region using an algometer with a 1 cm² rubber tip. Depression, Anxiety, Stress Scale (DASS 21) was used to assess differences in emotional status.

Results: There were no significant differences in PPT in the forearm region (FP:33.55N/cm²±12.15 vs LP:33.55N/cm²±13.65N/cm², t=0.509;p=0.979) and the lower back region (FP:56.85N/cm²±19.95N/cm² vs LP:58.93N/cm²±21.20N/cm², t=0.982;p=0.619) among participants in different phases of the MC. Additionally, no significant differences were found in depression ($\chi^2=1016.000$;p=0.392), anxiety ($\chi^2=972.500$;p=0.243) and stress (t=-1.038;p=0.302) between participants during the MC.

Conclusions: There were no significant differences in PPT between women in the FP and LP of the MC. There were no significant differences in emotional status among women during the MC.

I-C.23

CLINICAL APPLICATION OF THE N13 SOMATOSENSORY EVOKED POTENTIALS IN COMPLEX REGIONAL PAIN SYNDROME

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Background and aims: The N13 component of somatosensory evoked potentials (SSEPs) was shown to be increased after experimentally-induced central sensitization in healthy controls, possibly reflecting enhanced dorsal horn excitability. Whether the N13 poses a useful surrogate of central sensitization in chronic pain patients with complex regional pain syndrome (CRPS) remains to be demonstrated.

Methods: Twenty individuals with hand CRPS type 1 and 20 age- and sex-matched healthy controls (HC) will be recruited for this study. Pain phenotyping and quantitative sensory testing (QST) will be performed to detect hypersensitivities within the affected arm of CRPS patients. Additionally, the peripheral N9 component, the cervical N13 component and the cortical N20/P25 complex of the SSEP will be recorded after electrical stimulation of the median nerve from both arms (affected/unaffected). Presence, amplitude and latency of SSEPs will be analyzed.

Results: Data of eight CRPS patients and seven HC have been collected so far. All eight patients with CRPS showed clear signs of mechanical hyperalgesia. Preliminary results do not show increased N13 amplitudes after stimulation of the affected hand of CRPS (1.4±0.7uV) compared to their unaffected hand (1.7±0.9uV, n.s.) or HC (2.1±0.7uV, n.s.).

Conclusions: Unchanged amplitudes of N13 SSEPs in CRPS could either imply a lack of strong spinal sensitization in our current patients or that the used method is not sensitive enough to detect spinal hyperexcitability in chronic pain patients. Additionally, factors like medication associated reduction of SSEP amplitudes or peripheral impairments could dilute detectability of enhanced dorsal horn excitability in clinical pain cohorts.

I-C.24

„HOW SHOULD SHOULDER PAIN BE LABELED?“ THE PERSPECTIVE OF SHOULDER EXPERTS. A QUALITATIVE STUDY

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Background and aims: Shoulder pain represents a prevalent musculoskeletal condition, but there is limited consensus on diagnostic labeling for cases that are not linked to frozen shoulder, instability, or osteoarthritis. This study explores physiotherapists' perspectives on various diagnostic labels for non-specific shoulder pain, focusing on clinical utility, patient communication, and prognostic implications.